

**A STUDY OF STUDENT'S OPINION ON THE PARADIGM SHIFT IN
TEACHING AND LEARNING IN COVID 19 PANDEMIC W.R.T. DEGREE
COLLEGE STUDENTS IN KALYAN DOMBIVLI CITY**

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Abstract :

Education has undergone paradigm shift since COVID 19. The closure of colleges as a result of COVID-19 has been a significant global event. There were huge changes generated by this crisis. Using digital technology in higher education was a great challenge. There has been a sudden change in the mode of teaching learning from offline to online. The current research study aims to find the opinion of students of degree colleges about online learning and to know the challenges faced by them.

Key words: *paradigm shift, COVID-19, online learning*

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Introduction :

In the present crisis due to Covid-19, for professionals across industries it has been an easier transition as many of them work on their laptops and smart devices even in office. They can simply plug in at homes now. Certainly, what is missing is face to face, personal communication. But students have undergone far bigger alteration as learning has always been in classrooms earlier. From the Vedic times to the present, learning has been taking place in one mode communication with the physical closeness of teacher and student. The COVID-19 has resulted in sudden shut down of schools and colleges all across the world. As a result, education has changed radically, with the distinctive rise of e-learning, whereby teaching is undertaken remotely and on digital platforms. It is a sudden paradigm shift away from the classroom in many parts of the globe. For teachers, the shift to online education was a great challenge to rethinking lesson plans to fit a very different format. Some are still wondering whether the adoption of online learning will continue to persist post-pandemic, and how it would impact the global education market.

Review of Literature :

Abhinandan Kulal and Anupama Nayak in their research paper on the topic “A study on perception of teachers and students toward online classes in Dakshina Kannada and Udupi District” have analyzed students’ perception as positive perception based on all positive beliefs of students towards online class and negative perception based on all negative beliefs of an online course.

Hlamulo Wiseman Mbhiza in their paper on the topic “Shifting Paradigms: Rethinking Education During and Post-COVID-19 Pandemic” have studied measures taken by higher education institutions to support the online education.

G. Thiru Moorthy and S. Arulsamy in their paper on the topic “Understanding the paradigm shift in teaching and learning” said that utilization of technology alone can’t be a healthy paradigm shift in teaching and learning process. There is a need for reclaiming, revamping, rejuvenating the skills, ethics, social, cultural values, morality, patriotism and empathy. It is a need of the hour that modern technology in education should assist to traditional technology of education.

Objectives of Study :

- To study the opinion of students about online lectures
- To give suggestions for the implementation of right mode of teaching learning.

Research Methodology :

For data collection, both Primary & Secondary data was collected. Primary data was collected by floating the structured questionnaire on Google form. The Secondary data was collected from books, articles in journals and websites. For survey purpose, simple random sampling method was employed to select a representative sample. The respondents consisted of all degree college students from different colleges in Dombivli city. A sample of three hundred and eleven students from Commerce, Science and Arts Program was collected with the help of well-structured questionnaire.

Data Analysis :

Simple percentage method is used to analyse the data and get the opinion of students.

Findings :

Demographic profile of the respondents :

The demographic details of students were collected to know their background like gender, Area where they reside and they are admitted to which program.

From the data collected it was found that:

1. 39.5% were from Rural and 60.5% from Urban
2. 37.6% were Male and 62.4% were Female
3. 6.1% responded from Arts, 77.8% responded from Commerce and 16.1% responded from Science Program.

It was also found that:

1. 95.2% said that they have access to a device for learning online and 4.8% said they have no access.
2. 97.4% students use Smart Phone for online learning whereas the rest 2.6% students use Laptop, Desktop and Tablets.

3. 19.9% students said that the attendance of students for online lecture is very good, 47.9% said as good, 25.1% said the attendance is average and 7.1% said it is poor.
4. 30.5% students said that online learning is very effective, 55.9% said it is moderately effective and 13.5% said it is not effective.
5. 17.4% students said that many times they face technical difficulties like network connectivity etc. while attending online lectures, 66.2% said they faces some times and 16.4% said they never faced any technical difficulties.
6. 33.4% said many times they can concentrate properly on the topic taught in the online lectures, 58.5% said sometimes they can concentrate and 8% said they can never concentrate.
7. 43.7% students responded that many times their doubts are cleared immediately in the class in online teaching, 48.6% said sometimes their doubts are cleared and 7.7% said that never their doubts are cleared immediately in the class in online teaching.
8. 77.8% students said Yes for face to face meeting of students and teachers for better communication and understanding while 22.2% students said No.
9. 88.1% students said that Yes various teaching tools like PPT presentation, you tube videos, recorded lectures are effective teaching methods while 11.9% said No.
10. 72.3% said that Yes the study material of all the subjects are easily available in online classes while 22.7% said No.
11. 69.1% responded that Yes current system of online exam is a right way of testing the knowledge of students whereas 30.9% responded as No.
12. 65.9% students feel that Yes there is a need of traditional offline method of teaching while 34.1% students feel No.

Suggestions :

1. To maintain a high level of attendance, teachers should adapt lesson plans to stimulate interest in the subject, should create web and mobile-based tests, quizzes and surveys to encourage students to improve their knowledge and skills, keep parents always informed of absences, grade, and discipline issues via email and SMS alerts.
2. Technical problem like loss of connectivity, internet is sometime faced by students. Teachers can record their lectures and put it on Google classroom or WhatsApp group so that they can watch the lecture later.
3. In online learning there is no face to face contact. The teachers can make the learning more effective by showing PPT which may include some animation, pictures, diagrams and charts to make it more simple and interesting.
4. To hold the concentration of students in the online learning, the teachers should implement online interactive tools via chat, discussion forum, messaging, audio, and video which will make it easier for students to learn and understand and also to develop interest in learning.
5. The last 10 minutes of every lecture can be kept for question-answer and doubt solving session of the students. This will make the class more interactive and responsive.

Conclusion :

It was found that the students adapted quickly to the sudden shift to online mode due to the Covid-19 Pandemic. With the use of modern technology and tools they found the class interesting but a face to face contact with the teachers and friends were largely missing. The students believe that there should be traditional method of offline teaching with the use of modern methods of technology and teaching methods for better learning and understanding.

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Cite This Article:

Dr. Anuja Bapat, (2022). *A Study of Student's opinion on the Paradigm Shift in teaching and learning in Covid 19 Pandemic w.r.t. Degree College Students in Kalyan Dombivli city. Aarhat Multidisciplinary International Education Research Journal, XI (II), 11-14*